

**TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE TO SUPPORT TO INDUSTRIALISATION AND PRODUCTIVE
SECTORS (SIPS) IN THE SADC REGION**

Implemented by Consulting Group GmbH

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Final Report

Framework for Integrating MSMEs in RVCs

by

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Technical Assistance to SADC Secretariat on developing a framework and guidelines for integration and effective participation of MSMEs in regional value chains

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
ARV	Anti-Retroviral
CESARE	Cooperation for the Enhancement of Southern African Development Community Regional Economic Integration
EC	European Commission
EPZ	Economic Processing Zones
EU	European Union
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit GmbH
GVC	Global Value Chain
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
KII	Key informant interviews
MNE	Multi National Enterprise
MS	Member States
MSMEs	Micro Small and Medium sized Enterprises
NKE	Non-Key Expert
R&D	Research and Development
R&GVCs	Regional and Global Values Chains
RISDP	SADC Regional Indicative Strategic Development Plan
RQ	Research Question
RVC	Regional Value Chain
SADC	Southern African Development Community
SEZ	Special Economic Zones
SIPS	Support to Industrialisation and the Productive Sectors
VC	Value Chain

Executive Summary

1. Introduction

a. MSMEs to bridge the gap in SADC

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are defined according to the number of the company's employees, its capital turnover or balance sheet. The thresholds differ from country to country, generally depending on whether the country is developed or still developing. In the European Union for example, a micro enterprise employs fewer than 10 people and has annual turnover of about USD 2 million. A small enterprise is one, which employs a maximum of 50 people and has an annual turnover of maximum USD 12 million. A medium-sized enterprise in the same region employs up to 250 people and has an annual turnover of up to USD 300 million. In Africa, the thresholds are much lower. For example, in Botswana, a micro enterprise is a company with less than 6 workers and has annual turn-over of about USD 5,000. A small enterprise in the same country employs less than 25 people and has maximum annual turnover of about USD 130,000.

The fragmentation of production processes across national borders into global value chains (GVCs) has given rise to new opportunities for firms in both developed and developing countries to increase their participation in regional and global value chains (R&GVCs). In Southeast Asia, for example, regional and global value chains have played significant role in supporting economic development, allowing the region to achieve remarkable export-led growth, and become a leading investment destination for multinational enterprises (MNEs) (Nasir, et al., 2021).

Countries promote integration of MSMEs into regional and global value chains by creating policy and regulatory incentives, mainly in the areas of trade, investment, infrastructure, institutions, supplier strategies and governance. The SADC Regional Indicative Strategic Development Plan (RISDP) 2020-2030 envisages increased participation of MSMEs in the economy, playing critical roles as suppliers of inputs and services in regional value chains. MSMEs that are active in RVCs are also likely to attract more investment, which enables them to take positions in critical segments of global value chains (GVCs).

MSMEs make up the majority of enterprises in SADC and are the major source of employment. However, their contribution to GDP and exports is modest, mainly due to low productivity and lack of international competitiveness. Limited resources make it difficult for the MSMEs to comply with requirements of international certifications, rules, and principles. These challenges are generally attributed to the small size and limited experience of MSMEs, which constrain their access to scale and international markets. Yet participation of the MSMEs in regional and global value chains (R&GVCs) will help them reduce these constraints, e.g. by facilitating technology transfer and exposing the MSMEs to international markets for inputs, finance, intermediate and finished products. The MSMEs will have the opportunity to specialise in the production of intermediate outputs and act as suppliers to regional/international large firms. Participation in R&GVCs will also help the MSMEs attain international certification, which is currently a major hurdle.

In short, participation of MSMEs in R&GVCs leads to increased participation of the MSMEs in exports, productivity growth, innovation, employment generation and higher productivity, production efficiency, product quality, skills development, product diversification and access to new markets. These are mainly attributed to the inter-action that the MSMEs will have with large firms, including multi-national enterprises (MNEs).

SADC Members States have come up with several policies, regulations, and measures to encourage participation of MSMEs in national, regional, and global value chains. For instance, nearly all the member states at one point applied high tariffs and were actively involved in the drafting of model policy framework for integrating SMEs in regional value chains for the SADC Secretariat, providing local content requirements

with the objective of stimulating domestic sourcing from the MSMEs. However, such measures were counterproductive as forcing firms to source domestically resulted in loss of global competitiveness by the local firms, considering that domestic prices were often higher than those at the international market. The issue of high tariffs has however been addressed through the creation of the SADC Free Trade Area.

Nearly all SADC MS, including Botswana, Mauritius, Malawi, Zambia, and Zimbabwe have also come up with specific MSME policies that seek to promote the participation on the MSMEs in value chains at all levels. The policy interventions primarily focus on addressing market failures such as informational asymmetries, access to finance, supplier contracts, customs procedures, and other trade facilitation measures, which usually put the MSMEs at a disadvantage compared to large firms. Some SADC MS, including Botswana, Mauritius, Madagascar, Zimbabwe, and Zambia have created Special Economic Zones (SEZs) or Economic Processing Zones (EPZs) to promote foreign direct investment, employment creation, increasing exports earnings and enhancing participation of MSMEs in the value chains. A Special Economic Zone (SEZ) is a geographical legal area with liberal and special economic laws, policies, and regulations, which are different from the rest of the areas in a country (World Bank, 2011). The success in China has inspired African countries to adopt SEZs. However, the success in Africa has largely been affected by weak linkages with national, regional, and global economies, thereby limiting their macro-economic and developmental impacts.

Empirical evidence has shown that integrating MSMEs into regional and/or global value chains (VCs) through SEZs is hindered by the same problems affecting the rest of the economy, such as weak governance, inadequate infrastructure, institutional weaknesses, and weak linkages among the value chain players, among others (GIZ, 2021). Therefore, SADC MS needs to develop an actionable MSME VC integration framework that addresses these challenges, hence the need for this assignment. The framework needs to consider various aspects, including linkages between the MSMEs with large firms/multinational enterprises (MNEs), supplier contracts, linkages with investors and finance companies, collaboration with vocational training centres, higher learning institutes, business associations and regulatory bodies. The framework needs to review SEZ and cluster development strategies with the view to enhancing positive spill-overs on MSMEs. The framework must also consider compilation of supplier databases and support for obtaining certifications. An enabling policy environment should be put in place as the essential first step. It is within this context that the SIPS Programme seeks to develop an effective framework for integrating SADC MSMEs into the RVCs.

b. Leather value chain

The leather industry is the largest in South Africa, valued three times more than the meat industry (GIZ, 2021). However, most of the SADC member states are at the lower end of the value chain for leather, focusing on export of unfinished raw hide to countries where there is demand for leather, mostly Europe. Research has shown that exporting high-end finished product of leather would be more viable and command higher profits. South Africa and Tanzania are the only countries in the SADC member states that are functioning at all stages of the value chain with the other countries narrowly focusing on a few stages, mainly livestock farming or manufacturing (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2018).

Major challenges across SADC Member States are lack of good management practices, regional and international market access, and lack of sustainable financing arrangements. Other obstacles of the Leather RVC are inconsistent enforcement and compliance of policies and regulations. Additionally, the industry needs preventive and protective measures for the workforce through high quality occupational health and safety standards, this requires extensive human and institutional capacity, which is currently lacking.

To take full advantage of the regional value chain in SADC member states, policies and regulations need to be delivered that can look beyond the standard leather products and increase involvement at all points of

the value chain. Potential areas to explore is the production of hides and skins as non-leather products, increasing market shares of existing utilized tanneries and manufacturing of leather goods within the SADC member states.

The leather value chain in the SADC Member States is more prominent in South Africa, Tanzania, and Mauritius (SADC, 2019). The MSMEs in the Member States are dominant in the specific part of the value chain, mainly livestock herding and tanneries. Even then, MSMEs can be seen to be struggling, since they lack the necessary skills and financial support to bring in the latest technologies to improve the hide and skins for leather. Opportunities for MSMEs in the leather value chain lie in MSMEs focusing on the high-end side of the value chain, which would allow them better access to international markets (GIZ, 2021).

c. ARV (antiretroviral) value chain

Pharmaceutical manufacturing is relatively capital-intensive due to its highly technical and regulated nature. The ARV manufacturing value chain consists of nine segments. A full manufacturing facility needs significant production volumes and high-capacity utilization to achieve the economies of scale necessary to compete in the price-sensitive market. Given the industry context, MSMEs are not prominent within regional value chain and are marginalised into specific components of the value chain, mostly on the packaging side. In countries like South Africa and Tanzania, where the value chain is more apparent, the MSMEs are also limited as the larger international pharma companies are more dominant in the value chain (GIZ, 2021) (Nasir, et al., 2021).

For SADC member states, the ARV value chain is relatively small as infrastructure is weak in most countries, except for South Africa. South Africa is the biggest producer of ARVs within the SADC Member States requiring around one billion ARV tablets per year, with the highest number of HIV patients in the world. Due to intense global competition, the gross margin on ARVs is around 20-25% whereas other general pharma product is around 40-45%. Therefore, it is difficult for pharma manufacturers to dedicate their manufacturing plants solely to ARV production tablets.

Within the SADC Region, the general pharma production is weak. Local producers face many obstacles usually in the form of poor policy and regulatory framework, and weak economic indicators. Further challenges are related to (i) manufacturing and operation-capacity challenges, (ii) market and regulatory-related issues and (iii) financial issues.

For SADC member states to utilise the ARV value chain to its maximum potential, many aspects of the ARV Value Chain will need to be reviewed, particularly those to do with the policy and regulatory environment. Policies and regulations that allow governments to support MSMEs in the ARV manufacturing could help SADC Member States to produce locally and cater to the ARV sector where the SADC member states have some of the highest market.

d. The SIPS programme and context of this assignment

The Support to Industrialisation and the Productive Sectors (SIPS) is an overall programme supported by the European Union (EU) for the Secretariat of the Southern African Development Community (SADC) as approved by the European Commission (EC) in October 2017. The Programme addresses coordination and linkages failures between the regional and national levels, between the public and private sector and between the private sector in SADC Member States (MS), with a specific focus on the leather and associated value chains in the agro-processing sector, and antiretrovirals (ARVs) and associated value chains in the pharmaceutical sector. The SIPS Programme has three key result areas as follows:

- **Result 1:** Enhanced policy, regulatory and business environment on national and regional levels for development and sustainable operation of regional value chains (for selected products) in the agro-processing and pharmaceutical sectors.

- **Result 2:** Private Sector Participation in Regional Pharmaceutical & Medical Value Chains Enhanced.
- **Result 3:** Private Sector participation in Regional Leather Value Chain enhanced.

The SADC Secretariat is responsible for implementing Result 1 and collaborates with the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit GmbH (GIZ) in the implementation of some activities in Results 2 and 3.

2. Objective of the assignment

To develop a framework and guidelines for integration and effective participation of MSMEs in regional value chains. This will be delivered through:

- a. Analysing and reviewing current policies supporting the integration and participation of MSMEs in regional agro and pharmaceutical value chains
- b. Undertake benchmarking of best practices in the region
- c. Facilitate public-private sector dialogue in order to design and facilitate the adoption of a regional policy framework and guideline for the integration of MSMEs in regional value chains

3. Methodology

Desk review and stakeholder consultations were carried out to gather data. This type of methodology was agreed at the kickoff meeting between the NKE, TAT and SADC secretariat on [REDACTED]

Before the research could be conducted, eight (8) research questions were developed to assist in designing and framing the assignment methodology. These eight (8) questions are:

1. To what extent do the selected RVCs exist in the region, how is this distributed across each SADC member state?
2. What are the specific challenges and opportunities inherent within the selected RVCs?
3. What is the importance of MSMEs in the selected RVCs and what challenges and opportunities do they face?
4. What is the policy governance system at both regional and national levels which supports or hinders the selected RVCs?
5. What are the most important barriers to upgrading? What are specific strategies the government can implement to increase MSMEs involvement in the RVC?
6. To what extent can MSMEs can participate in the RVC and GVC? What policies and programme support would they need?
7. What are the best practices to integrate MSMEs in the RVC? To what country or organisations can the SADC be benchmarked against?
8. What regional and national policy framework can be developed to support MSMEs benefit from the selected RVCs and how can they be imbedded into other sectors?

An evaluation matrix provides more detail and can be viewed in the [REDACTED]

a. Desk review

The NKE reviewed several documents associated with both the leather RVC and the ARV RVC. The first category of documents reviewed are project related:

- SIPS Terms of Reference for NKE Assignment
- IGC Regional Value Chains in East Africa: Summary Report
- UNCTAD Identifying Regional Value Chains in Leather and Leather Products in Africa
- UNCTAD Transforming Southern Africa – Harnessing Regional Value Chains and Industrial Policy for Development
- European Parliament briefing on Global and Regional Value Chains

- The Role of Trade Policies in Building Regional Value Chains – Some Preliminary Evidence from Africa (UNCTAD/SER.RP/2017/11)
- SADC Protocol on Industry
- SADC Protocol on Trade (1996)
- RISDP 2020-30 (SADC/SM/1/2020/6A)
- South Africa Department of Trade and Industry (the dti), Department of Science and Innovation and SANBio Report on the Regional Leather Value Chain (Nov 2019)
- SADC Profiling of the Regional Agro-Processing Value Chains in the SADC Region
- SADC Industrialization Strategy and Roadmap 2015-2063
- Formulations of Industrialisation Programme for the SADC Secretariat
- GIZ Antiretroviral value chain inception report

The second category of reports and articles were researched by the NKE, and the full list can be viewed in the

b. Online survey

An online survey was developed as the fastest and quickest way to get responses from the relevant stakeholders or KIIs. The survey needed to include questions that could be asked to any consultant both in the leather sector and the ARV sector. Key questions that were asked of each stakeholder can be seen below. The full interview can be seen [online](#) done through Google Forms and in the annexes.

The consultants were given a brief background through email as well as on the survey itself on why the surveys were being held. The survey was structured with two specific information in mind: the first part of the survey asked general questions about the stakeholder and the company and country (s)he worked at and the second part focused on the questions NKE had designed specifically about MSMEs in their respective value chains. All questions were mandatory.

The main questions asked on the survey were:

1. Our research has shown that MSMEs can play a crucial role in bridging the gap that is currently visible within the value chains. Where do you see MSMEs potential within the value chain that could actually help improve it?
2. MSMEs struggle with getting the right support to get their business to be successful. This support can be improved through current policies and regulations. Are there any regulations or policies that you believe that need to be implemented that can help MSMEs be more visible within the value chain?
3. What type of support do you believe MSMEs will need the most to integrate into the value chain?
4. Some of the biggest challenges that are being faced currently within the value chain are getting the right technology, the right education and skills and getting the right people. What type of programs do you believe can help close the gap through current policies or future policies?
5. Can you give an example of a programme that you would believe help close the gap?
6. Looking at the current policies that are in place, especially for trade policies, do you believe these polices are adequate enough to help MSMEs be part of the value chain competition?
7. Do the current trade policies favour larger companies and/or international companies?
8. What can be implemented that would allow the trade policies to benefit MSMEs as well as other larger organisations within your value chain?
9. Are there any risks with the current policies and regulations within your sector?
10. How can these risks impact MSMEs who are trying to enter the value chain?

11. Where in the value chain do you see the most risk?
12. In your opinion, how do you believe can these risks be reduced?
13. If the SADC region was to standardise trade policies across the region, do you see added value to such a move?
14. What would be the implications, if any? Would this move be of a benefit to you and your company, or would it be a hindrance?
15. How will standardising trade policies across SADC impact MSMEs?
16. As national value chains turn regional and global, what current policies and regulations are in place that protect the existing national network?
17. Will competing on a regional level make it harder for MSMEs to enter the value chain?
18. From your viewpoint, what are the advantages and disadvantages for MSMEs entering a regional value chain?
19. As we evaluate the current policy framework, how best do you believe can we integrate MSMEs within the value chain? What tools and/or skillsets is required for such an integration to take place?
20. Can you give an example of current policies that you believe are supportive of integrating MSMEs? Are there any that are successful?

c. Stakeholder interviews

4. Study Findings

The research for this study was conducted during the months of February and March 2022 where COVID-19 pandemic is still at large although many countries have relaxed their stances. However, precautions were advised where necessary to keep COVID-19 safety in mind. For this reason and the limited time taken for this research, the most effective and efficient method for gathering data was utilized. Most of the work has been done through desktop research, followed by an online survey and follow-up interviews where possible.

The following sections will provide detailed analysis based on the study findings.

a. The eight (8) research questions

The eight (8) research questions that were created during the writing of the inception report were key research questions that would help understand what is the best way to develop a framework and guideline for the integration of MSMEs in SADC regional value chains. **Table 1** below shows the different areas of the value chain we believed the questions would target and the responses to questions are given below.

Table 1 - The eight RQ and the different areas of the value chain they target

#	Eight (8) research questions pre-developed to understand RVCs in SADC	Different areas of the value chain the questions are most likely to impact				
		Technical	Financial	Regulatory	Skills Development	Value Chain Network
1	To what extent do the selected RVCs exist in the region, how is this distributed across each SADC member state?					✓
2	What are the specific challenges and opportunities inherent within the selected RVCs?	✓	✓	✓	✓	
3	What is the importance of MSMEs in the selected RVCs and what challenges and opportunities do they face?	✓			✓	
4	What is the policy governance system at both regional and national levels which supports or hinders the selected RVCs?			✓		
5	What are the most important barriers to upgrading? What are specific strategies the government can implement to increase MSMEs involvement in the RVC?		✓	✓	✓	
6	To what extent can MSMEs can participate in the RVC and GVC? What policies and programme support would they need?		✓	✓	✓	
7	What are the best practices to integrate MSMEs in the RVC? To what country or organisations can the SADC be benchmarked against?		✓	✓		
8	What regional and national policy framework can be developed to support MSMEs benefit from the selected RVCs and how can they be imbedded into other sectors?			✓		

RVC Challenge #1 – Value Chain Network

Leather: the regional value chain in SADC member states is much stronger than in other areas of Africa, however, the value chain is quite disparate between the member states. With South Africa and Tanzania having almost complete value chain present within their countries, other member states have one or two aspects of the value chain. Even then, the focus of the other countries within the member states are more on livestock and tanneries. This is also linked with the countries GDP and how developed these countries are overall in terms of infrastructure, resource availability, transportation network, labour, and financial resources. Many of the countries rely on South Africa the most within the Southern African states, and most also import hides from China.

Figure 1 - A general value chain of the leather sector

MSMEs can help bridge the gap by focusing on the areas of the value chain that are non-existent within the Member States. This in turn can help keep the cost of production low since the value chain is national and less expenditure on importing or exporting product. For example, when livestock are ready to be slaughtered, animal trading occurs where livestock is mainly exported, due to higher demands abroad, little to no slaughtering infrastructures, or the slaughtering process takes place on micro level of individual butchers rather than abattoirs. By building abattoirs or increasing the number of slaughter places within the country can keep livestock within the country and thus reducing costs. One other aspect MSMEs can help in the development of the value chain is to focus on the higher end of the value chain: manufacturing and retail and trade. Usually, member states of SADC value chain end at tanning or trading of skins and hides depending on the country. By bringing in manufacturing, SADC member states will no longer be relying on exporting just skins and hides but actual high-level goods.

ARV: The pharmaceutical sector is a high risk, high capital sector, where it is difficult and expensive to have the whole value chain network within one country. The nature of the pharma manufacturing is that most manufacturing plants do not cater to a specific drug manufacturing, but several lines will be producing several drugs being manufactured at the same plant. Within the SADC member states, pharmaceutical manufacturing is available in South Africa, Tanzania, Namibia, and Zimbabwe, however, their manufacturing plants do not focus on ARV alone. ARV manufacturing is marginal, with the few ARC specific manufacturing done locally do not produce enough in volume. The supply is too low within the member states do the demand is justified through importing ARV tablets from India and China. While certain protocols and regulations are in place to accommodate ARV tablets availability, accessibility is still difficult especially since Southern Africa is noted for its high HIV rate.

Figure 2 - A general value chain of the antiretroviral (ARV) sector

MSMEs can help bridge the gap by buying into the higher end of the value chain focusing on packaging, logistics and sales. These segments of the value chain can reduce costs, increase accessibility and bring in domestic competition which can eventually lead to the global market. MSMEs need to be adaptable to a quick changing market and can shift their business models to accommodate current events which these segments will foresee. The beginning of the value chain is less likely to change rapidly, requires high capital and generally involves more than one stakeholder working together from different

RVC Challenge #2 – Technical

Leather: One of the biggest technical challenges faced by the SADC member states is how to turn raw hide into leather product good that can further enhance the countries in the value chain. This challenge would require looking at the different segments of the value chain that can help bring the end product – leather goods - for exporting and trading. The challenge also lies in keeping the process as sustainable as possible. While certain countries, such as Morocco has its natural tanneries still in place and functioning, process leather is deemed harmful to the environment due to its large usage of water, harmful chemicals and chemical wastage not properly disposed and managed. The leather sector is also facing challenges from the artificial leather industry, gaining traction due to it being environmentally friendly and synthetically produced in the lab. Infrastructure wise, upgrading current facilities to accommodate high end products could deem expensive.

MSMEs can help bridge the gap by focusing on manufacturing and retail and trade segment of the value chain. This would help shift the regional market from the main exporter of hides and skins to high end leather products. The shift can also accommodate the regional demand of leathery goods.

ARV: There are many technical challenges faced by the ARV sector within the SADC member states. While most countries within SADC may not have the whole value chain excluding South Africa and Tanzania, the infrastructure needed to develop the value chain on this aspect will require a lot of government and private sector support. The value chain requires R&D, of the products, which would mean state of the art labs that are internationally accredited and FDA approved, which can also cover the APIs (Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients) and FDF (Formulation of Final Dosage) segments of the value chain. Manufacturing can be seen in South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe, but the other member states should have their own manufacturing plant to reduce costs and less reliance on the importing of the ARV tablets. Distribution and Sales of the ARV tablets is also a challenge as they are only sold in pharmacies in certain areas. People who live in rural areas would have limited access to these tablets and do not have the necessary form of transport to reach towns and cities where ARV tablets may be available.

MSMEs can help bridge the gap here by creating labs at a micro level that can focus on specific aspects of R&D. It would also allow MSMEs to collaborate with international pharma companies and other regional pharma companies. MSMEs can also close the gap of distribution and sales by developing efficient methods to bring ARV tablets to people in rural areas.

RVC Challenge #3 – Financial

Leather: Financial support is a huge challenge the current leather sector changes. The different segments within the value chain need the necessary channels and programs that can help fund and support current companies and organizations working in the industry.

ARV:

RVC Challenge #4 – Regulatory

Leather:

ARV:

RVC Challenge #5 – Skills Development

Leather:

ARV:

b. Survey Analysis

The survey sent out to the different stakeholders in the leather and ARV sector was met with low expectations. At the time of this writing, we only received three (3) responses to the survey where the correspondents were all male working in the leather sector. We received no response from the ARV sector. There could be several reasons for such a low response. Direct emailing and reaching out the stakeholders could cause low responses as the NKE is not well known with the stakeholders as opposed to getting an email from SADC themselves requesting for participation.

The survey was sent out at short notice, 10 days prior to writing the report. The three stakeholders submitted the survey responses three (3) days prior to writing the report. However, the three responses were enough to give preliminary understanding and support to the recommendation and guideline that will be developed through data gathered by desktop research.

The full survey and its response survey can be seen in the

Since the response of the survey was from the leather sector, I will be focusing on the leather sector in my analysis. The survey response was given from a General Manager, President, and a Project Manager. One was a private company, one was an association, and one was from the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and Environment of South Africa. While all three correspondents gave useful information, the correspondent from the ministry had the most insights and gave detailed answers compared to the other.

One of the questions that was asked regarding the type of support MSMEs need to integrate into the value chain, all three correspondents chose financial, showing the importance of efficient and transparent financial channels needed for MSMEs to be successful in the leather value chain. This answer can be seen in figure 3 below.

Figure 4 below shows the response that skills development should be the focus of policy and programmes to help MSMEs have the right skills needed to enter the leather market and compete at the regional level with other stakeholders. This shows us that in order for the right skills to be developed and utilized, programmes focusing on delivering workshops, information sharing and courses providing certificates or accreditation need to be delivered for MSMEs to succeed.

What type of support do you believe MSMEs will need the most to integrate into the value chain
3 responses

Figure 3 - Response summary of question 17 from the online survey

Some of the biggest challenges that are being faced currently within the value chain are getting the right technology, the right education and skills...he gap through current policies or future policies?

3 responses

Figure 4 - Response summary of question 18 from the online survey

Question 25 from the survey asked where in the value chain was the most risk. All three correspondents picked production followed by trade policies and regulations as well as the international. This can be seen in **figure 5** below. This insight allows us to see that technical aspects of the value chain needs to be priority for SADC to improve the leather sector by allowing MSMEs to focus on the production aspect.

Where in the value chain do you see the most risk? (You may select more than one option)

3 responses

Figure 5 - Response summary for question 25 from the online survey

Questions that were asking about policies and regulations for MSMEs to integrate in the value chain gave a clear indication that awareness on existing policies does not exist. From the three (3) correspondents, only the ministry correspondence had awareness and understanding of the challenges and risks that current policies give to MSMEs, the other correspondents were either not aware or were not sure. This gives a clear indication that moving forward, organizations need to have more exposure to existing policies and programs so they have a better understanding and use it to help MSMEs enter the value chain.

Although the above analysis is limited due to the small number of responses, it is still adequate enough to develop a baseline for how to improve and develop guideline for better integration of MSMEs into the value chain.

- c. Best practices from other regions

5. Recommendation

- i. Streamline the current policies and regulations (hampering rather than helping)
- ii. Create more channels and programs for financial access
- iii. Increase the current number of workshops/courses/programs for skills development (incubation and acceleration programs)

6. Conclusion

7. References

8. Annexes